

EMIRA: Creating the EMI Research Archive

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Abstract

The English Medium Instruction Research Archive (EMIRA) is an open dataset designed to improve access to and synthesis of research on English Medium Instruction (EMI) in higher education. In recent years, both EMI and EMI research output have grown substantially. Yet EMIs fragmented and context-dependent nature makes it difficult for researchers and educators to locate relevant studies. EMIRA V0.1 contains data 1,054 peer-reviewed journal articles published up to 31/12/2023. This paper describes the creation of the archive as part of a systematic review. It also outlines how this archive is structured, its key use cases and limitations, and provides a roadmap for the archive's future. EMIRA is intended as a transparent research infrastructure for both teachers and researchers to facilitate evidence synthesis, identify research gaps, and support inclusive global engagement with the field.

Introduction

English medium instruction (EMI) is a topic which has grown in the research literature from a trickle of studies in 2005 to 250 studies a year in 2023 (Hampson and McKinley 2025). The same period has also seen a huge growth in EMI itself, often driven by the neoliberalisation of higher education (Chang, 2025; Wingrove et al., 2024). While this growth in research has been advantageous in advancing our understanding of this increasingly important phenomenon, it has made it difficult for researchers, let alone practicing teachers, to keep up with the large amount of research being released every week. Furthermore, as Hampson and McKinley (2024) highlight, there is a risk of contextuality in research meaning that EMI in one context can be quite a different thing from EMI in another context.

Given this, there is a need for researchers and teachers to be able to identify EMI research easily and quickly. In particular, it is important to be able to identify papers from a certain region or country, or which cover a certain topic or use a certain methodology. This paper describes the creation of a dataset designed to help with these issues. The present paper covers EMIRA V0.1, consisting of 1054 studies and covers up to the end of 2023. It describes the creation of the dataset, how it can be used, its current limitations, and plans for its expansion. The data set described in this study is available at:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Oa4bQPNXCVVv7B5kRCzX7ysQdc4qNPM4EWV26XOqiW0/edit?usp=sharing>

Methodology

EMIRA was created as part of a PhD project involving a mixed method, methodology and approach (Hampson & McKinley, 2023) systematic review. This involved several phases described in this chapter:

1. Finding papers
2. Sorting papers
3. Coding papers
4. Indexing papers

Stage one—Finding papers

Papers were initially identified using Scopus and Web of Science. These two databases were selected because they are well-regarded and they allow for easy indexation of papers. The search terms used were:

English and ("medium of instruction" OR "medium instruction" or "medium education") and ("university" OR "higher education")

- Excluding Notes, reviews and editorials.
- Only in English
- To 2023 (inclusive)

These terms were selected in line with the purpose of this systematic review: to explore the phenomenon of the growth of EMI research in universities. Because this dissertation is interested in EMI research qua EMI research and because of the already substantial number of papers included, other terms such as ‘English taught’ and ‘CLIL’ were not included in these search terms. This represents a gap in the dataset.

Stage two—Sorting papers

The initial search returned 1,447 results from Scopus and 1,309 from Web of Science resulting in a pool of 2756 records. After the removal of 777 duplicate papers using EndNote, a pool of 1979 records remained. The details of these papers were then exported to an Excel file with papers placed in a pseudorandom order and then given an index number. In a study referencing the dataset heavily, it is possible to reference specific papers from this list using squared brackets. For example, [2] can refer to paper 0002 from this list. This allows future authors using EMIRA to distinguish between citations that refer to the review dataset itself and those that engage with individual study findings.

These 1,979 papers were then screened initially by AI (see Hampson, Cargos and McKinley, forthcoming) excluding 174 records. A further 200 reports were excluded by

me during full text screening. 455 entries which were not journal articles were removed, firstly to focus on a consistently accessible set of texts, second to avoid longer texts (e.g. monographs) having an undue influence on the results of this study, and third because of practical constraints. Additionally, 96 articles were unavailable. This left a pool of 1,054 papers (see also figure 1).

Figure 1
PRISMA chart of screening process (Page et al., 2021)

Stage three—Open coding

The new smaller pool of papers was then read and coded in the same random order they had been numbered in. This allows for the removal of bias that might come from simply searching for papers, where the most popular papers are likely to come up first. The initial coding looked for anything interesting and explanatory with in-vivo coding used heavily in the early stages. As trends began to emerge, similar codes were

combined and renamed. As codes were developed, they were placed into themes, and sometimes sub-themes. As I approached 40 papers coded (approximately 320,000 words), a stable set of themes and codes had emerged. Based on the principle of referential adequacy (Lincoln & Guba, 1985), an additional 20 papers were coded (total approximately 480,000 words). Only minor changes were made during this time—e.g. changing ‘prior exposure to EMI’ to ‘prior exposure (and lack of)’ to highlight that this was often a challenge to learning. Given this stability, I decided to move forward with purposive sampling.

There are several additional considerations that had to be taken during this process. Already coded papers were periodically revisited to check that the codes remained an accurate description of them. During this process, special attention was paid to negative cases, i.e. cases that go against the code. In some cases, this led to sections of studies being coded in a certain way which might not fit with a broader theme. For example, the code of ‘teacher centred classroom’ is coded under the theme of challenges, but in some cases, students found a lack of teacher-centredness in the classroom challenging. In these cases, the code was applied and then differing perspectives were compared.

When coding papers, I decided to focus on data from the papers. In practice, this meant that literature reviews were ignored. The reason for this is to avoid repeating received wisdom in the field. While it may be interesting explore the discourse around EMI in literature reviews relying on them would place an undue bias towards highly cited studies.

This open coding process resulted in the following set of themes:

Methods:

Coding: Studies where themes are identified from data.

Interview: Research involving conversations between researcher and participants including interviews, focus groups, and stimulated recall.

Observation: Studies observing EMI contexts, e.g. direct observation or video recordings.

Questionnaires: Refers to studies using questionnaires with qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-methods questions.

Testing: Papers testing students’ or teachers’ abilities or comparing groups in EMI contexts.

Textual Analysis: Focuses on analysing authentic written texts by participants, such as essays, journals, or forum posts, excluding transcribed interviews or observations.

Research foci:

Challenges: Explores student difficulties or barriers in EMI contexts

Describing: Describes or characterizes EMI practices, policies, or contexts.

Effects: Studies the outcomes or impacts of EMI implementation that are not explicitly covered by 'efficacy'.

Efficacy: Evaluates the effectiveness of EMI in promoting English ability and subject knowledge learning.

L1 Use: Investigates the role and implications of using the first language in EMI settings, including translanguaging.

Attitudes: Analyses stakeholders' perceptions toward EMI.

Pedagogy: Examines how best to teach in EMI contexts.

Growth: Describes reasons for the uptick in EMI programs.

Strategies: Focuses on ways students cope with studying in an EMI context.

These themes formed the basis for the following stages.

Stage four—Indexing

The next stage uses a version of purposive sampling adapted from grounded theory. Purposive sampling requires access to further data on specific topics of interest. The most typical way of achieving this during a grounded theory is through asking questions about those issues during interviews. For EMIRA, this is achieved by searching through the corpus of papers for ones on a specific topic, a task greatly aided by the indexing conducted in stage three. This was achieved across the set of 1054 papers using GenAI (see Hampson, Cargos and McKinley, forthcoming) to:

1. Categorise papers by methodology. This was achieved by using GenAI to put papers into categories based on the categories created in stage three.
2. Categorise papers by research question. Research questions were first extracted using GenAI. These were then manually categorised based on the categories generated in stage three.
3. Extract research location from papers.

Columns

Information about each column in the dataset can be found in Table 1.

Table 1

Description of dataset columns.

Column	Description
ID	Numeric ID for referencing each study. Studies were placed in a pseudorandom order and then assigned ID numbers. ID numbers are nonconsecutive when records were filtered out during the systematic review process.
Year	Year of publication.
Title	Title of the article.
Author	Authors' names.
1st Author Institution	The name of the first author's institution, taken from OpenAlex
Journal Name	Name of the journal where the article was published.
DOI	Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for the article.
OA URL	If available, this provides a link to an open-access version of the article. Filtering out 'NA' allows users to identify accessible papers.
Open Alex ID	OpenAlex ID for the article (if available).
IF	Journal-level Impact Factor, based on OpenAlex citation data. For papers under 3 years old, citation count may be used as a proxy.
Citations	Number of citations based on Web of Science or Scopus listing (as of time of coding).
FWIF	Field-Weighted Impact Factor: calculated as a paper's impact factor divided by expected citation rate for a paper published that year. A FWIF of 1 is average. An FWIF of 2 indicates a paper's impact factor is twice what we would expect based on its year of publication. An FWIF of 0.5 indicates an impact factor that is half of what we might expect.
FWCI	Field-Weighted Citation Impact: calculated as citations divided
Affiliation	First author's institutional affiliation (based on OpenAlex metadata where available).
Subregion	World Bank subregion of the study's research location.
Research Location	3-letter ISO country code representing where the study was conducted. If multiple countries, they are comma-separated. Use "contains" filters rather than strict matches.
Challenges	Binary code: 1 = the study discusses challenges faced in EMI contexts.
Describing	Binary code: 1 = the study aims to describe EMI contexts, policies, or practices.

Column	Description
Effects	Binary code: 1 = the study investigates the impacts of EMI beyond language/learning efficacy.
Efficacy	Binary code: 1 = the study evaluates EMI's effectiveness in improving English and/or content learning.
L1 Use	Binary code: 1 = the study discusses first language use, code-switching, or translanguaging in EMI settings.
Attitudes	Binary code: 1 = the study analyses stakeholders' perceptions, opinions, or affective responses toward EMI.
Pedagogy	Binary code: 1 = the study discusses or recommends teaching strategies for EMI.
Growth	Binary code: 1 = the study explains or documents the expansion of EMI programs.
Strategies	Binary code: 1 = the study explores how students or teachers cope with EMI, including learning or teaching strategies.
Coding	Binary code: 1 = the study used qualitative coding to derive themes from data.
Interview	Binary code: 1 = the study uses interviews, focus groups, or similar methods.
Observation	Binary code: 1 = the study includes classroom or video-based observation of EMI in practice.
Questionnaire	Binary code: 1 = the study employs surveys or questionnaires (quantitative, qualitative, or mixed).
Testing	Binary code: 1 = the study includes formal testing of language or content learning outcomes.
Textual Analysis	Binary code: 1 = the study analyses written texts (e.g. essays, forum posts, journals), excluding interview transcripts.

Use Cases

There are many potential use cases for this database centred not only around systematic review, but literature reviews more generally. Some of these are highlighted below.

- The most common use of this database would be to identify research on a theme. For example, Amy Bao, who agreed to serve as a beta tester for the achieve was interested in how much work in EMI looks at emotions. This type of search can be done by:
 - Filtering by one or more of the research foci.
 - Searching within abstracts.
- Another use is to search for articles from a particular country. This can be done in terms of where the first author is based (affiliation) or through research

location. Both of these can be accessed through filters, but for research location, it is best to search for the three-letter character string rather than using the drop down. Because papers were in many cases assigned more than one location, selecting 'HKG' from the drop down would not include papers conducted in Hong Kong and another location.

- For practicing teachers, who may not always have access to journal articles, the option to search for research conducted in a local context in combination excluding entries with a blank record for 'OA Link'

To filter, it is necessary to either download a copy of the database or to select row 3, click 'Data' and then 'Create filter view'.

Limitations

While I believe this dataset will be useful to researchers in EMI, there are also notable limitations. Many of these may be resolved in future versions of this dataset.

Dates: The current dataset goes up to the end of 2023. This means that it is rapidly becoming out of date, particularly when we consider the year-on-year growth in EMI research output in recent years. I am aiming to update the dataset by roughly one year every six months, with the hope that it will soon not lag so far behind reality. I will aim to get studies from 2024 included in the database by January 2026

Databases: The current version of EMIRA uses Scopus and Endnote as sources. However, these are limited, particularly when it comes to research from the Global South (see Hampson & McKinley, forthcoming). As such, future updates of this project will also include OpenAlex as a source of papers.

Article types: The current dataset includes only journal articles. This was a pragmatic choice: journal articles are more consistently structured, readily indexed, and typically peer-reviewed. However, this approach excludes substantial work found in books, edited volumes, doctoral theses, and conference proceedings — especially those from underrepresented regions. A future aim is to expand EMIRA to incorporate such sources, though this will require additional protocols for indexing and coding.

EMINOs: Some of the studies in the database are what I have been terming 'EMINO', EMI in name only, studies. These will be conducted in an EMI context, but not be a study of EMI as a phenomenon. I have included these, first, because it is hard to draw a hard line between relevant and not relevant and, second, because while a given study may seem extremely tangential to me, it may seem extremely relevant for another teacher or researcher.

Timeline for future updates

Late 2025: EMIRA 0.2 will seek to refine the current dataset and uncover any errors. I will also aim to update where the database is stored from Google Documents to

Datsette and to begin to offer larger .csv versions of the same dataset through GitHub that can be used for critical bibliometric analysis.

January 2026: EMIRA 1.0 will include the present database as well as studies from 2024. This will include a wider range of databases than EMIRA 0.X versions.

July 2026: EMIRA 2.0 will be updated with studies from 2025.

January 2027: EMIRA 3.0 will be updated with studies from 2026. At this point, the archive will have 'caught up' with reality.

Moving forward: I will look into options for including studies beyond journal articles. I will also explore options for having the database updated on a monthly basis.

Conclusion

EMIRA 0.1 represents a valuable first step in establishing a transparent, reusable and grounded database of EMI studies. While the current version of this dataset is limited in that it does not include studies from 2024 and 2025 and only covers Web of Science and Scopus, the plans for expansion represent an opportunity to grow this dataset to be more comprehensive and more equitable. This delivers on two urgent needs for the field: first, better visibility of research from often ignored contexts, and second, easier access to evidence to inform good practice and decision making.

Chang, Y.-l. (2025). Beyond common sense: An inquiry into neoliberalism and English as the medium of instruction in Taiwanese higher education. *Higher Education Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41307-025-00398-z>

Hampson, T., & McKinley, J. (2023). Qualitative and quantitative are data types not paradigms: An MMA framework for mixed research in applied linguistics. *LEARN Journal: Language Education and Acquisition Research Network*, 16(2), 1-7.

Hampson, T., & McKinley, J. (2024). Systematic review, systematic bias? An example from EMI research. *Language Teaching*, 1-9.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444824000338>

Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. SAGE Publications.

Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hrobjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S.,...Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *Syst Rev*, 10(1), 89.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-021-01626-4>

Wingrove, P., Zuaro, B., Nao, M., Yuksel, D., Littvay, L., & Hultgren, A. K. (2024). University autonomy is a predictor of English medium instruction in European higher education. *Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-024-01333-8>